

LINGUISTIC CATEGORY OF WRITTEN TRANSLATION

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ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to the subject of written translation is the text. Textual material can be divided into groups according to the stylistic criterion, which takes into account the role played by one or another category of linguistic means, depending on the general nature of the content.

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The subject of written translation is the text. Textual material can be divided into groups according to the stylistic criterion, which takes into account the role played by one or another category of linguistic means, depending on the general nature of the content. What linguistic means are taken into account in such a classification? These are terms, phraseology, characteristic of this genre, syntactic constructions prevailing in it, figurative and emotionally colored means of the dictionary, etc.

Usually text material is divided into three groups:

- newspaper-informative, documentary and special-scientific texts;
- journalistic works;
- works of fiction.

It should be noted that there are transitional or mixed types of material (for example, in fiction - works on production topics with an abundance of terms; in scientific literature - works of a popular genre using expressive means of artistic imagery). In all types of material, commonly used vocabulary is presented, since it

forms the basis on which understanding is generally possible, the background against which various elements of the vocabulary of the language are distinguished.

Let us give a general description of all groups of textual material.

The first group: newspaper-informative, documentary and special-scientific texts the presence of terms that stand out against the background of common words;

the presence of some phraseological complexes more frequent in this genre due to its purposefulness (e.g., as we have seen, should be borne in mind, it should be noted, as already mentioned above, etc.);

frequent mention of proper names (personal and geographical), names of institutions, public organizations (they occupy an intermediate place between a term and a proper name, often make up whole phrases);

the absence of stylistically colored words (archaisms, poeticisms, etc.);

use of words in their direct meanings.

Second group:

Publicistic works (socio-political, philosophical content, literary criticism, newspaper and magazine journalism, works from the field of oratory) are created as a means of influencing the general readership, they relate to issues of a wide scale;

combine the features of scientific speech (terminology) and the features of the language of fiction (figurative elements and emotional coloring);

- relatively moderate use of terms;

- wide use of common vocabulary;

- wide use of words with a variety of stylistic coloring.

- The third group of text material:

- the absence or great rarity of terms;

- widespread use of dialectisms, professionalisms, archaisms, words of foreign origin, elements of vernacular, etc.;

a wide range of use of various possibilities of word usage - direct and figurative meanings of words, etc.

Let us characterize three groups of textual material in terms of their grammatical features.

The first group is characterized by an orientation towards written language with a predominance of complex sentences and without phraseological units that would indicate a connection with the style of oral speech. For syntax, the completeness of sentences is indicative. Describing the method of presentation adopted for such material, A.L. Pumpyansky summarizes that: "The main task of scientific and technical literature is to bring certain information to readers as clearly and accurately as possible. This is achieved by logically substantiated division of the factual material, without the use of emotionally colored words, expressions and grammatical constructions.

In the second group of textual material, syntax tools play a much more active role. Sentences are focused on bookish and written speech, but they may show features typical of the oral-speech style, namely, appeals to the reader (listener), emotionally colored exclamatory or interrogative-rhetorical constructions may appear (e.g. To be or not to be "But what to do? Who is to blame?").

In the third group - in fiction - the diversity of speech styles is manifested in the exceptional breadth of syntactic means. Here they combine the features of both book-written and oral colloquial speech:

- transitions from long and complex sentences to simple and short ones;
- alternation of those and others;
- a combination of literary-correct syntactic forms with various ellipses, broken sentences.

Based on this, we can say that the task of translation remains a stylistic task for any kind of translated material. The translator's task is to select vocabulary and grammatical possibilities. This selection is determined by the general orientation of the original and its genre affiliation and compliance with the norms that exist for the corresponding variety of texts into the target language.

LITERATURE

1. Қўлдошев Ў. (2023). ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДАГИ ФРАЗАЛИ ФЕЪЛЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ТАРЖИМА МАШАҚҚАТЛАРИ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(12), 65–68. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7902159>.
2. Кулдошов У. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида конверсивлик ва антонимлик ҳодисаси //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 3 (80). – С. 67-73.
3. Kudratovich D. N. SOME VIEWS ABOUT TRANSLATION STRATEGY //International Congress on Models and methods in Modern Investigations. – 2023. – С. 15-17.
4. Daminov N. SCIENTIFIC VARIETIES OF TRANSLATION STRATEGIES //Конференция: Союз Науки и Образования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 25-28.
5. Даминов Н. К. СИНХРОН ТАРЖИМАНИНГ АСОСИЙ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //PEDAGOGIK ISLOHOTLAR VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 66-69.
6. Kasimova A. N., Rakhmonova G. N. THE USE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AS HEADLINES OF MASS MEDIA //Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 153-158.
7. Kasimova A. N., Nurullayeva D. S. H. NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRENDS IN WORD FORMATION (BASED ON TEXTS IN THE MEDIA) //Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 130-133.
8. Nosirovna K. A. et al. NEWSPAPER STYLE. THE TRANSLATION ISSUES OF LEXICAL UNITS AND WORD COMBINATIONS IN NEWSPAPER TEXTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 285-287.
9. Xidirovich N. X., Daminov N. Q. SINXRON TARJIMON NUTQIGA QO ‘YILADIGAN TALABLAR //IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 21-27.